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Cost Focus Strategy And Blue Ocean Strategy On Efficiency Of Hospitality Industries In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the cost focus strategy and blue ocean strategy on efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra State. The researcher developed three objectives which were to: Assess the effect of cost focus strategy on efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra State. Examine the effect of blue ocean strategy on efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra State. Examine the effect of combination (hybrid) strategy on efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra State. This study is anchored on Resource-Based View Theory. Data were generated through primary and secondary sources. The method for data collection was the questionnaire which was administered randomly among the staff of the hospitality firms. The population of the study was four hundred and twenty-six (426). Three hundred and seventy-seven (377) (88.49%) copies of questionnaire were retrieved out of the copies of questionnaires distributed. The hypotheses were tested using regression analysis method at 0.05% level of significance. Findings from the study revealed that Cost focus strategy has significant effect on efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra State, (t-test, 8.433, p=000); Blue ocean strategy has significant effect on efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra State, (t-test, 2.283, p=017); Combination (hybrid) strategy has significant effect on efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra State, (t-test, 3.717, p=003). The study concludes cost focus strategy and blue ocean strategy has significant positive effect on efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra State. The study recommended that The study recommends that Hospitality industries employ cost focus strategy effectiveness and swiftness in operations to accommodate a broader range of customer segments along their business growth path. Management should also see to it as a matter of urgency to innovatively deliver a cutting edge services that outstands their competitors hence encourage acquisition of more customers. Corporate enterprises should focus on combination strategies that improve their profit margins, quality of service and customer satisfaction.

Keywords: cost focus strategy, blue ocean strategy, efficiency, Combination (hybrid) strategy hospitality industries

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The hospitality industry plays a vital role in the socio-economic development of Nigeria, particularly in states like Anambra where tourism, business travel, and urban expansion have increased demand for lodging, food, and recreational services (Atueyi, & Mbanefo 2025). The sector contributes significantly to employment generation, income creation, and regional development. However, the competitive environment of the hospitality industry in Nigeria has intensified due to the entry of new hotels, guest houses, restaurants, and short-let apartments, all struggling to attract and retain customers (Nwangwu,

Ohanyere, Nwangwu, & Atueyi, 2025). In this highly competitive environment, achieving efficiency defined as the optimal use of resources to maximize customer satisfaction and profitability has become an essential goal for survival and growth (Ifechukwu-jacobs, & Atueyi, 2024).

To remain competitive, many hospitality businesses adopt strategic approaches that can enhance their operational efficiency and market positioning. Among these are the Cost Focus Strategy and the Blue Ocean Strategy, two distinct yet complementary approaches that can influence how firms achieve superior performance and sustainability (Ifechukwu-Jacobs, Arinze, & Nwangwu, & Atueyi, 2025).. The Cost Focus Strategy, one of Porter's generic strategies, involves targeting a specific market segment and seeking to offer products or services at the lowest cost within that niche. In the hospitality industry, this might mean focusing on budget-conscious travelers, streamlining operations, reducing waste, negotiating better supplier deals, or utilizing technology to minimize operational costs (Onya, Dr Arinze, & Atueyi, 2025). By controlling costs while maintaining acceptable service quality, firms can achieve cost efficiency, which enhances profitability and customer loyalty in price-sensitive markets. On the other hand, the Blue Ocean Strategy emphasizes creating uncontested market spaces rather than competing directly within existing industry boundaries. It encourages firms to innovate and differentiate their services in ways that make competition irrelevant (Ohanyere, Arinze, & Atueyi 2025). For hospitality firms in Anambra State, a blue ocean approach could involve developing unique customer experiences, leveraging local culture and cuisine, introducing digital innovations such as smart rooms or online concierge services, or blending hospitality with tourism and event experiences. The essence of the blue ocean approach is value innovation simultaneously pursuing differentiation and low cost to create new demand and operational efficiency. Despite the potential of these strategies, many hospitality businesses in Anambra State continue to struggle with inefficiency due to high operating costs, inconsistent service quality, poor innovation culture, and inadequate strategic management. While some firms attempt to cut costs, they often compromise service quality. Others try to innovate without aligning their innovations to cost structures, leading to inefficiency and financial strain. This indicates a lack of balance between cost management and strategic innovation precisely where the combination of cost focus and blue ocean strategies could yield optimal results.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to examine cost focus strategy and blue ocean strategy on efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra State. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Assess the effect of cost focus strategy on efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra State.
- ii. Examine the effect of blue ocean strategy on efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra State.
- iii. Examine the effect of combination (hybrid) strategy on efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra State.

1.3 Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses will guide the study

Ho₁: Cost focus strategy has no significant effect on efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra State.

Ho₂: Blue ocean strategy has no significant effect on efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra State.

Ho₄: Combination (hybrid) strategy has no significant effect on efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Market Focus Strategy

Focus strategy is one that targets certain segments of the markets by differentiating customer needs to be able to serve them at their best affordable prices. According to Little child (2018), firms focus on a selected product range, customer group, geographical area or service line. Operating in a niche market, this strategy advocated for a growing market share where markets seem unattractive or are overlooked by larger competitors. Notably, focus strategy enabled a company to maximize its special unique distinctive capability to gain new market share (Kuratko, Hornsby & Hayton, 2015). In the focus strategy, a firm

targets a specific segment of the market (Porter, 1996). The firm can choose to focus on a select customer group, product range, geographical area, or service line (Martin, 2019). For example, some service firms focus solely on the service customers (Stone, 2015). Focus also is based on adopting a narrow competitive scope within an industry. Focus aims at growing market share through operating in a niche market or in markets either not attractive to, or overlooked by, larger competitors. These niches arise from a number of factors including geography, buyer characteristics, and product specifications or requirements. A successful focus strategy depends upon an industry segment large enough to have good growth potential but not of key importance to other major competitors. Market penetration or market development can be an important focus strategy. Midsize and large firms use focus-based strategies but only in conjunction with differentiation or cost leadership generic strategies.

2.1.2 Blue Ocean Strategy

The Blue Ocean Strategy is a marketing tactic that was first presented by Renee Mauborgne and Chan Kim in 2005. It offers a fresh avenue for organizations to thrive by entering uncontested markets with little competition. It represents the entire uncharted market. Value innovation, the production of high performance, and strong demand are its defining characteristics. The characteristics of a distinct market area and value innovation are experienced without regard to market limits. The metaphor shows a blue, placid, and welcoming water in contrast to Kim and Mauborgne (2021) defined the blue ocean strategy as the idea that businesses can create new growth opportunities by refocusing their efforts from strategies meant to outperform or beat the competition to calculated actions meant to create new, uncontested market spaces with large potential and boundaries. Moreover, businesses function within a market universe that can be conceptualized as consisting of two oceans: blue oceans, which symbolize non-existent industries in uncharted market areas, and red oceans, which represent all currently operating industries (Kim and Mauborgne, 2021).

The need to create blue oceans is growing, according to Lee and Gaynor (2016). These dynamics can be found in all industry environments, where productivity has increased due to accelerated technological advancements, globalization has made goods and services almost universally accessible across regions, accelerated commoditization of goods and services has led to price wars and declining profit margins, and so on. Differentiating brands has grown more challenging in most product and service categories, and price is now the primary factor influencing revenue growth and profitability (Muhammad, 2020).

2.1.3 Combination (Hybrid) Strategy

A combination competitive strategy involving high level of emphasis on both cost-leadership and differentiation strategies simultaneously should be distinguished from “stuck-in-the-middle” strategy where a firm fails to successfully pursue both cost-leadership and differentiation strategies (Acquaah & Ardekani, 2016). A combination strategy has been shown to be viable and profitable (Miller & Dess, 2013; Wright, Kroll, Tu, & Helms 2021). Since cost-based and differentiation-based advantages are difficult to sustain, firms that pursue a combination strategy may achieve higher performance than those firms that pursue a singular strategy. Pursuit of a differentiation strategy for low-cost firms will help minimize their vulnerability due to reliance on cost-based advantages only (Yasai-Ardekani & Nystrom, 2016). A hybrid strategy seeks simultaneously to achieve differentiation and low price relative to competitors. This success strategy depends on the ability to deliver enhanced benefits to the customers with low price while achieving sufficient margins for reinvestment to maintain and develop bases of differentiation. A best-cost provider strategy: giving customer more value for the money by offering upscale product attributes at a lower cost than rivals. Being the best cost producer of an upscale product allows a company to under-price rivals whose products have similar upscale attributes. This option is a hybrid strategy that blends elements of differentiation and low-cost in a unique way (Thompson et al, 2012).

2.1.4 Efficiency

Organizational efficiency comprises the actual output or results of an organization as measured against its intended outputs (or goals and objectives). According to Richard *et al.* (2019), organizational efficiency three specific areas of firm outcomes: financial performance (profits, return on assets, return on

investment, etc.); product market performance (sales, market share, etc.); and shareholder return (total shareholder return, economic value added, etc). Organizational efficiency is the ultimate dependent variable of interest for researchers concerned with just about any area of management (Devinney *et al.*, 2010). This broad construct is essential in allowing researchers and managers to evaluate firms over time and compare them to rivals. In short organizational efficiency is the most important criterion in evaluating organizations, their actions, and environments.

There are several methods that have been put forward for measuring organizational efficiency at employee and organizational level. One group of performance measures which is traditional is financial and accounting based and these were based on the assumption that firm performance is only measured in quantifiable units. These financial measures include income or sales from operations, rate of return on investment and residual income (Warren *et al.*, 2018). Without disregarding the merits of the financial and accounting measures in assessing performance, the fact that they were cost based and backward looking provided little motivation (Manzoni & Islam, 2019). There are now new enhanced metrics to measure performance being adopted by financial specialists and these include measures such as activity based costing and economic value added (Beheshti & Beheshti, 2010). Another recent concept to measure performance is that balance scorecard.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Resource-Based View Theory

The resource-based view (RBV) of Wernerfelt (1984) suggests that competitiveness can be achieved by innovatively delivering superior value to customers. The extant literature focuses on the strategic identification and use of resources by a firm for developing a sustained competitive advantage (Barney, 1991). The core idea of the theory is that organizations should look within at the resources and potential it already has instead of focusing on the competitive external environment. In strategic management research, RBV theory has emerged as one of the theoretical perspectives used to explain the continuity in inter-firm performance differences (Barney and Griffin, 1992).

According to RBV theory, firms have collections of unique resources and capabilities that are valuable, rare, inimitable and non-substitutable and which are able to provide them with a sustainable competitive advantage. As a result, resources are real and intangible assets that a company owns or controls, whereas capabilities relate to a company's ability to exploit and combine resources through organizational processes in order to meet its goals (Amabile et al, 1996). It is crucial to research how internal and external resources can be influenced by competitive strategy and enable an organization's capabilities to improve innovation performance by using RBV theory in this study (Galbreath 2005).

According to Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998), the term "intellectual capital" refers to the knowledge and knowing capability of a social collectivity, such as an organization, intellectual community, or professional practice", while social capital is defined as "the sum of the actual and potential resources embedded within, available through, and derived from the network of relationships possessed by an individual or social unit". Intellectual capital is a valuable resource in the form of accumulated knowledge which is embedded within an organization, while social capital resides in the relationships firms have with their network partners. Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998) argued that innovation is the ultimate outcome of the creation of new knowledge which results from the combination and interaction between intellectual capital and social capital of firms. SMEs also are endowed with these two sets of capital or resource that require effective and efficient management to ensure the enterprises competitive favorably and perform.

Relevance of Research Based Theory

The resource-based theory or resource-based view helps in determining the resources available within the firm and relates them with the capabilities of the firm in a silent manner. This brings into consideration, the profitability and the value factor associated with the firm. As per this theory, the competitive advantage can be delivered to an organization when the organization is able to utilize its resources in a unique and valuable manner than the competitors of the firm. This theory clarifies that the entire firm that has gained excellent capability is due to the extraordinary and non-substitutable slot of resources available to the firm. This brings the firm more success in the emerging economy of the world. Resource-based

theory, in other words, is regarded as one of the processes which is based on inside-out strategy. The strategy focuses on the methods through which the firm collects resources.

2.3 Empirical Review

Karaev, (2023) delved into the impact of competitive strategies on firm performance. The study employs Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Smart-PLS with 325 respondents from the beverage industry. By keeping in sight how market orientation and innovation on their own authority yield mediating effects, light can be shed on what matters for a firm to triumph in this demanding industry. The conclusion drawn suggests that companies embracing a realistic market-oriented outlook in their product planning and advertising, combined with centering on novelty, are better placed to stay successful within this fiercely competitive business space.

Daahir (2021) examined the impact of cost leadership strategy on organizational performance of telecommunication companies in Mogadishu-Somalia. The second objective was the impact of differentiation strategy on organizational performance of telecommunication companies in Mogadishu-Somalia. The third objective was the impact of focus on strategy on organizational performance of telecommunication companies in Mogadishu-Somalia. The target population was 100 and the sample size was 60 respondents. The study used descriptive method and 20 questionnaires were distributed. Descriptive and correlation analysis was used. The study found that cost leadership strategy, differentiation strategy and focus on strategy have significant positive relationships on organizational performance of telecommunication companies in Mogadishu-Somalia. Finally, the researcher found that the competitive strategy has significant positive relationships on organizational performance of telecommunication companies in Mogadishu-Somalia.

Kpurunee, Amadi and Kpurunee (2023) examined the relationship between competitive strategies and organizational performance in corporate enterprises in Nigeria. The survey was based on five selected entrepreneurial companies with a sample size of 15 staff. Questionnaires were administered to the staff of the selected companies. Two hypotheses were formulated and tested, and the statistical tool Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to test the strength and direction of the relationship between the variables. Findings revealed that there is a relationship between competitive strategies and organizational performance. Therefore, it was concluded that to thrive in today's business environment, corporate enterprises must adopt suitable competitive strategies, as these make up the life wire of an organization to create value, outwit competitors, and increase market share. Thus, we recommended that corporate enterprises should focus on strategies that improve their profit margins, quality of service and customer satisfaction; they should invest in customer relationship management to retain existing customers and up sell additional products or services; and they should leverage technology to enhance operational efficiency, reduce costs and improve product/service quality.,

Gatimu and Amuhaya, (2022) examined the effect of Cost leadership, Differentiation and Focus Strategies on the performance of SMEs in Kiambu County. The study was guided by Porters Competitive Strategy Theory, Resource Based View Theory and Resource Dependence Theory. A descriptive research design will be used targeting 889 SMEs belonging to different sectors; manufacturing has 113, agricultural has 226, essential services that include private schools and health facilities have 217, general merchandise like shops and supermarkets have 106, commercial services and other service industries are a total of 227. Proportionate sampling technique was used to select the sample size. Data was collected using questionnaires and then analyzed using correlation and regression analysis. Data was presented in form of means and standard deviation by means of tables. The findings of the study confirmed that Differentiation, Cost leadership and Focus strategy had a significant influence on the performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Kiambu County. The study therefore recommends that the government comes in handy to support the SMEs by providing legislation aimed at providing a conducive environment to allow for full operationalization of Competitive strategies which would consequently translate to national economic growth.

Gwangwava and Zororo (2021) studied the impact of competitive strategies and innovation on firm performance. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire designed on a five point liker scale. One hundred and fifty employees, mainly those in charge of operations up to Chief Executive Officers who were knowledgeable about competitive strategies participated. Fifty firms operating in textile and clothing manufacturing provided the basis for the research. The structural equation modeling was employed using the least squares. The results show that focus and differentiation strategies have a positive direct relationship with firm performance and innovation. However cost leadership has indirect relationship with firm performance and a positive relationship with innovation which in turn improves firm performance. Implementation of the three generic strategies enables managers to gain competitive advantage for their firms although attention needs to be paid to innovation which acts as an enabler between the competitive strategies and firm performance.

Ibrahim and Oundo, (2020) examined the applicability of competitive strategies in sugar industry. Desktop analysis methodology was used through meta-analysis. From the reviewed literature, it revealed that organizations that use competitive strategies realize better performance than those that doesn't. This study is relevant to the policy makers for decision making, and it is also important to the researchers as it provides a platform for further studies. It is relevant for the managers as they can apply competitive strategies in sugar manufacturing firms. It also provides a chance to the managers of different sugar manufacturing firms to compare their performance with other countries that perform relatively better in sugar sector. The study recommends that sugar manufacturing firms should use competitive strategies in order to realize better performance. In conclusion, from the reviewed literature through meta-analysis, competitive strategies have a positive impact on performance of an organization.

METHODOLOGY

3.1: Research Design

The design that was adopted in this study was the descriptive survey research design where data concerning competitive strategy were collected. The primary source of data that was used in this study was from questionnaire. This is because of the nature of the variables that were used.

3.2: Population of the Study

The study focus on classifications of hotels described as 'hospitality house' within the Centra Business District of the Anambra state. The available information from the hospitality association of Anambra state chapter is 213 hotels of this category. In each hotel, the study targeted either the manager or deputy manger. The target population therefore was 426 persons.

3.3: Method of Data Collection

Quantitative data on the influence of competitive strategies on the performance of hospitality industries in Anambra state was collected using a structured questionnaire in order to allow for descriptive analysis from the responses. The choice for the questionnaire as a data collection tool will be founded on the fact that it is suitable for collecting a large amount of data from respondents within a short period of time.

3.4: Method of Data Analysis

The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation and percentages. Inferential statistics such as t-tests were also used. The significance level was set at $p < 0.01$ for every statistical set. The specific effect of independent variables vis-à-vis the dependent variable was tested through the multiple regression analysis.

Decision rule: we will accept H_0 , if p-value is greater than 5% level of significance; otherwise we will reject H_0 , to accept H_1

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Table 4.1.1 Summary of the Regression Result

The result of the multiple regressions formulated in chapter three is presented in the tables below

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				Durbin-Watson	
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2		Sig. F Change
1	.721 ^a	.520	.516	.48642	.520	134.559	3	373	.000	1.542

a. Predictors: (Constant), CBS, CFS, BOS

b. Dependent Variable: EFF

Table 4.1.1 shows that R² which measures the strength of the effect of independent variable on the dependent variable have the value of 0.52%. This implies that 52% of the variation on competitive strategy is explained by variations in cost focuses strategy, blue ocean strategy and combination strategy of hospitality firms in Anambra. This was supported by adjusted R² of 0.51%.

Test for autocorrelation: This is used test whether errors corresponding to different observation are uncorrelated. If the value of the durbin-watson from the regression result is close to 2 no autocorrelation in that regression result, but if it deviates significantly then there is autocorrelation. The Durbin-Watson statistic (D.W) of 1.6 reveals no autocorrelation in the models. Hence, the result is good for business analysis because the Durbin Watson result is 1.543

4.1.2 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	95.512	3	31.837	134.559	.000 ^b
	Residual	88.254	373	.237		
	Total	183.767	376			

a. Dependent Variable: EFF

b. Predictors: (Constant), CBS, CFS, BOS

The f-statistics value of 134.559 in table 4.1.2 with f-statistics probability of 0.000 shows that the independent variables has significant effect on independent variables such as cost focuses strategy, blue ocean strategy and combination strategy can collectively explain the variations in firm efficiency.

4.1.3 Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	.330	.087		3.781	.000	.158	.502
	CFS	.639	.035	.737	8.433	.000	.571	.707
	BOS	.006	.023	.011	2.283	.017	.051	.038
	CBS	.036	.021	.067	3.717	.003	.005	.076

a. Dependent Variable: EFF

A’p priori Criteria: This is determined by the existing business theories; it also indicates the signs and magnitude of the business parameter under review. In table above, we found out that cost focus strategy has a positive sign given its value as .639; this implies that a unit increase in cost focus strategy increases the efficiency by 63%, this conform to the a’ priori expectation. Blue ocean strategy has a positive sign given its value as .006; this implies that a unit increase in Blue ocean strategy increases the sustainability by 6%, this conform to the a’ priori expectation. Combination strategy has a positive sign given its value

as .036; this implies that a unit increase in Combination strategy increases the efficiency by 36%, this conform to theoretical expectation.

T- Statistics: The t-test is used to measure the individual statistical significance of our explanatory parameter in the model. From table Coefficients above cost focus strategy (CFS) is 8.433, this is statistically significant, this suggest that it contribute significantly to efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra state. Blue ocean strategy is 2.283 this is statistically significant, this suggest that it contribute significantly to efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra state at 5% level of significant. Combination strategy is 3.717 this is statistically significant, this suggest that it contribute significantly to efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra state at 5% level of significant.

Test of Hypothesis

Test of Hypothesis Three

Ho₁: Cost focus strategy has no significant effect on efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra State. Cost focus strategy has a t-statistics of 8.433 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that Cost focus strategy has no significant effect on efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra State

Test of Hypothesis Four

Ho₂: Blue ocean strategy has no significant effect on efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra State. Blue ocean strategy has a t-statistics of 2.283 and a probability value of .017 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses and conclude that Blue ocean strategy has significant effect on efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra State..

Test of Hypothesis Five

Ho₃: Combination (hybrid) strategy has no significant effect on efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra State.

Combination (hybrid) strategy has a t-statistics of 3.717 and a probability value of .003 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses and conclude that Combination (hybrid) strategy has no significant effect on efficiency of hospitality industries in Anambra State.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study established that company identifies the segments of the market that their business can perform best. They also provided ways through which they get to determine the segment that best suits them. One of them was through Recognizing Varying Needs of Clients and Customers based on their demographics, geographic, behaviour, and Psychographic bases (lifestyle, values, personality). The second method was analysing needs to aid in determination of the niche- it is crucial for a business to analyse the needs and wants of various markets before they determine their own niche. A blue ocean exists when there is potential for higher profits, as there is now competition or foreign competition. The strategy aims to capture new demand and to make competition irrelevant by introducing a product with superior features. It helps the company to make huge profits as the product can be priced a little steep because of its unique features. The strategy is not about operational effectiveness -- trying to be better, faster, or cheaper than a competitor. This is simply being more efficient than competitors. Nor is a strategy about benchmarking or trying to do the same things as your competitor but doing them better. Combining strategy and efficiency is an essential element of achieving business success. Ensuring that business processes and operations align with the organization's overall strategy can help maximize efficiency and achieve desired outcomes. Analyzing and optimizing processes can lead to increased efficiency by reducing waste, eliminating non-value-adding activities, and streamlining operations. Implementing appropriate technologies, such as automation, data analytics, or cloud computing, can help increase efficiency by reducing manual tasks, improving decision-making, and enhancing communication. Combining strategy and efficiency is a critical component of business success. By aligning operations with strategic objectives, optimizing processes, and leveraging technology, organizations can achieve greater effectiveness and competitiveness. Organizations that effectively balance strategy and efficiency are well-positioned to

respond to market changes, seize opportunities, and outpace their competitors. Continuous evaluation and adaptation of strategies and processes are essential for maintaining a competitive advantage and achieving long-term success. The study recommends that Hospitality industries employ cost focus strategy effectiveness and swiftness in operations to accommodate a broader range of customer segments along their business growth path. Management should also see to it as a matter of urgency to innovatively deliver a cutting edge services that outstands their competitors hence encourage acquisition of more customers. Corporate enterprises should focus on combination strategies that improve their profit margins, quality of service and customer satisfaction.

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